

Exploring Social Change and Class Distinctions in Modern Literature as a Catalyst for Cultural Understanding

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Abstract:

The correlation between actuality and portrayals of severe societal conditions stems from an inherent desire to directly confront unsettling truths. Realism is motivated by the desire to portray an unadorned perspective of society, compelling readers to actively address the portrayed concerns and cultivate empathy and understanding. Amidst a world that is becoming more fractured and unpredictable, realism contributes to a wider cultural effort to confront and understand this complexity. Amidst the swift societal changes, realism aims to establish a semblance of organization and understanding, serving as a method to comprehend and analyze the perplexing parts of life.

This study intends to analyze how the two authors reflect the concept of "realism" in their novels by examining the topics of "social change" and "depictions of class distinctions." The article aims to explore how these writers utilize realism to depict and analyze societal issues, class interactions, and the challenges encountered by regular folks, by examining the motifs in their works. This analysis aims to clarify how realism in literature functions as a powerful tool to reveal deep insights into the human experience, provoke introspection, and contribute to wider discussions on societal progress and the depiction of social classes. The study aims to shed light on the lasting importance and impact of realism in modern literary landscapes by examining the perspectives and practices of the writers.

Keywords: Realism, the human condition, social difficulties, socioeconomic differences, and harsh realities are some of the topics discussed.

Introduction

Ian Watt's influential book, *The Rise of the Novel* (1957), thoroughly examines the development and widespread appeal of the novel as a literary genre from the 19th century onwards. Watt specifically investigates the rise of 'realism' as a prominent literary movement during this period. Watt argues that the novel aims to accurately reflect reality by providing an unbiased portrayal of human experiences (54). However, it may be argued that the three classifications of institutions and practices - dominant, residual, and emergent - are essentially interconnected. Charles Dickens's novel *Hard Times* demonstrates the fusion of traditional love themes with contemporary genres to create a compelling depiction of realism.

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In her 2007 editorial titled "New Perspectives of Indian English Writings," Malti Agarwal argues that Indian English Literature maintains robust associations with the indigenous cultural identity of the nation. It offers a venue to illuminate the enduring concerns and injustices that are essential to contemporary India. Renowned authors like Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao, R.K. Narayan, Khushwant Singh, Nirad C. Chaudhary, Manohar Malgonkar, Amitav Ghosh, Salman Rushdie, and many more have received praise for their skill in portraying modern society with precision in their literary works (Beaumont, 1910).

Although the number of Assamese English writers included in the canon of contemporary Indian English Literature is minimal, they diligently tackle themes of violence and regional bias in Assam. Mitra Phukan, a renowned translator and children's novelist explores the Assam Movement in her highly praised novel *The Collector's Wife* (2005). Aruni Kashyap, a first-time author, vividly depicts the most grim period in contemporary Assamese history in his novel *The House with a Thousand Stories* (2013). The book encompasses themes of state terrorism, violence, counter-memory, and ethics. Literary works build a social reality by accurately and precisely depicting human experiences, situations, and societal conventions, capturing authenticity to actual life or the truth of how things are. The objective of realist fiction is to accurately reflect the actual state of reality, with a specific focus on the commonplace actions of ordinary persons. Realistic literature aims to expose the complexities and difficulties of society by portraying its less attractive features, such as brutality, depravity, and life in the lower social classes.

History acts as a valuable storehouse of life's intricacies, necessitating the reexamination of the past to comprehend the present. In his book *Beginning Theory*, Peter Barry (2008) observes that postmodernists support a critical reassessment of history using irony and experimentation as guiding principles. This approach is evident in post-colonial writing, as authors strive to regain and reinterpret their historical narratives. Frantz Fanon contends that the retrieval of one's historical background is crucial for colonized folks to ascertain their voice and identity. Assam, an area known for its varied cultures, traditions, languages, ethnicities, and complex history, presents a combination of cultural abundance and conflicts, often accompanied by violence and discord. The historical events of the past continue to have a significant influence on the people of Assam. Assamese writers, who were involved in India's colonial history, aim to reaffirm their cultural legacy and ensure that their perspectives have a significant impact on postcolonial Indian literature (Mukherjee, 1985).

An important turning point in Assam's history after colonial rule was the Assam Movement, mostly led by the student community of Assam through the All-Assam Students Union. Operational from 1979 until August 15, 1985, this movement sought to tackle the problem of unlawful immigration of foreign individuals, particularly from Bangladesh and Nepal, into Assam. The campaign aimed to tackle their involvement in the election process and advocated for the expulsion of all undocumented migrants existing in Assam. The profound impact of this movement is effectively depicted in Dr. Manirul Hussain's book *The Assam Movement: Class, Ideology, and Identity*. Mitra Phukan's novel, *The Collector's Wife*, powerfully depicts the impact of the movement in the fictional hill town of Parbatpuri, Assam, which is affected by the insurgency. The protagonist, Rukmini Bezboruah, observes the wide-ranging consequences of the Assam Movement with a strong perception of reality.

“... she looked at the eager, bright young faces of the boys and girls, she couldn't help noticing the facial features and contours before her. The almond eyes, the golden skins of the Mongoloid, the curly hair of the Austric, the dark complexions of the Dravids, and the fine features and fair colouring of the Aryans, were all present in the crowd of young faces before her. And they wanted to rid the land of foreigners!” (91)

The emergence of the United Liberation Front of Asom (ULFA) on April 7, 1979, led by Bhimkanta Buragohain and other prominent individuals, has been a major source of strife in Assam's political arena. The ULFA's main goal was to build an autonomous and sovereign Assam, which led the Indian government to officially ban the organization in 1990, classifying it as a terrorist group. To counter this rebellion, the government utilized clandestine tactics, using former ULFA members who had surrendered to execute extrajudicial killings, with a specific focus on the relatives of current ULFA members. The period characterized by state-approved homicides came to be recognized as the "Secret Killings of Assam."

In his 2009 book titled "Secret Killings of Assam," Mrinul Talukdar defines these secret killings as a sequence of organized actions carried out by the state administration, employing members of SULFA (Surrendered ULFA) and security forces, under the guise of counter-insurgency operations. The government rationalized these measures as a means of seeking punishment for the acts of terrorism supported by ULFA, particularly targeting ULFAs, the individuals who had surrendered from ULFA. The clandestine assassinations had a tremendous effect, instilling dread and uncertainty within the populace of Assam. Unsuspecting family members of ULFA militants were targeted, and the phrase "secret killings" became

synonymous with one of the most sinister periods in Assam's political history—a time that the people of the state would prefer to forget.

From 1998 to 2001, the term "secret killings" caused fear and suffering among the population of Assam. The environment was filled with intense fear, and a sense of uncertainty loomed over their daily existence. They lived in a state of perpetual peril, struggling with the frightening possibility of not surviving until the next morning (Sinha, 1979). The egregious savagery of these homicides has profoundly impacted the blameless individuals involved, resulting in enduring emotional wounds for those who were there throughout the kidnappings and killings. The recollections of the violence persisted in tormenting them, and the mere reference to "covert assassinations" evoked a sense of fear, serving as a chilling reminder of a distressing era that inflicted profound psychological scars. In his work *The House with a Thousand Stories*, Aruni Kashyap skillfully combines his creativity with the harsh reality of covert killings, creating a captivating setting. By skillfully integrating various elements, he successfully draws attention to the atrocities of this sombre period in Assam's history and emphasizes the lasting influence it had on the lives of its residents.

Both *The Collector's Wife* by Mitra Phukan and *The House with a Thousand Stories* by Aruni Kashyap are firmly rooted in the recent history of Assam, specifically during times of political turmoil. These novels explore difficult topics like as immigration, the Assam Movement, terrorism, and extortion, portraying a powerful depiction of the social environment filled with fear, anxiety, and glimpses of optimism throughout the late 1970s and the entire 1980s.

Mitra Phukan, in *The Collector's Wife*, fearlessly uncovers two divergent streams of patriotism that characterized the era of political insurgencies in Assam. The first form refers to a sincere manifestation of patriotism exemplified by individuals such as the students of DS College, who wholeheartedly prioritize the well-being of their motherland. The second expression is a deceptive display of patriotism, embodied by individuals such as Arnob Chakravarty, the English instructor, who uses the appearance of serving the nation to further their hidden objectives, motivated by undisclosed intentions. The socio-political context of that time had a great impact on the young people of Assam, causing them to shift their ambitions and engage in pointless and often cruel activities. A significant number of young individuals have enlisted in different terrorist organizations, participating in acts like armed robbery,

extortion, and kidnappings, which highlights the decline of moral principles in society (Misra 1987).

The story also sheds light on the presence of Surrendered Ex-Ultras, individuals who were once militants who claimed to have given up their weapons, yet continued to engage in violent and criminal activities while pretending to be integrated into society. The surrounding ambience fostered a dystopian and apocalyptic community in Assam, characterized by widespread fear, ubiquitous surveillance, and innate mistrust. An essential motif in the story is the idea of totalitarian patriotism when individuals who represent themselves as patriots exercise authoritarian control while pretending to promote the interests of a "Golden Homeland." The general public has been deceived into thinking that the cash obtained through extortion is used for the benefit of society, thereby maintaining a circle of false information and propaganda.

Both works vividly depict Assam's socio-political realities during that chaotic period, exploring its impact on individuals, society, and the fundamental nature of patriotism. These novels serve as reflective mirrors of the difficult times Assam experienced, offering important insights into identity, values, and the consequences of political upheaval on everyday lives. The novel *The House with a Thousand Stories* by Aruni Kashyap prominently focuses on the war between ULFA and SULFA in Assam. This conflict sheds light on the subtle complexity of the modern society in Assam, where violence deeply affects the fabric of the society.

The novel takes place during the late 1990s when the Indian government was accused of carrying out extrajudicial killings to suppress armed dissent. It courageously questions the official accounts and explores the internal tensions of the human mind. Aruni Kashyap shifts the attention towards the infringement of human rights instead of just criticizing governmental policy. This method highlights the tendency for individuals to frequently be used as pawns and controlled by government authority.

The story unveils the intricate web of conspiracy, portraying the clandestine assassins not as mysterious individuals, but rather as prominent individuals inside the government. This highlights the lack of genuine confidentiality regarding their acts and emphasizes the involvement of individuals in positions of authority. The novel explores the conflict between different social classes in society, particularly the exploitation experienced by workers by wealthy capitalists while adhering to the principles of socialist realism. This method is

supported by establishing connections between the activities of the Indian government and the colonial British, highlighting the shared experiences of marginalized individuals in Assam who have suffered human rights abuses akin to the oppression faced by subalterns under colonial rule.

The tale highlights the persistent disregard of the North-East region by the central government, which is a contributing reason to the oppression experienced by the people of Assam. The characters' quest for parity, protection, and constancy reflects the yearnings of the wider community. Although the final lines of the novel provide a feeling of conclusion, there is still a persistent inquiry: does the narrative genuinely conclude at that point? The reference is from Agarwala's work in 2007. The metaphor of imprinting on the earth and crushing dry leaves implies the lasting influence of these occurrences, raising uncertainty over the true attainment of justice. The pursuit of justice and equal rights continues unabated, as the echoes of history resonate in the lives of the people of Assam. The novel's depiction of this sombre moment in Assam's history serves as a heartbreaking reminder of the urgent need for enduring transformation, striving towards a society emancipated from the clutches of violence and injustice.

Representation of Women in the Novels of Pukhan and Kashyap

The novels illuminate the representation of women in Assamese society during the depicted era, which is marked by conservatism and marginalization. Mitra Phukan's novel, *The Collector's Wife*, and Aruni Kashyap's book, *The House with a Thousand Stories*, both shed light on the difficulties and oppression experienced by women as a result of cultural conventions, religious customs, and male control.

The characters Oholya-jethai and Moina-pehi in *The House with a Thousand Stories* represent the typical women of Assamese society. Oholya-jethai, who is subjected to racial prejudice, experiences mistreatment from her boyfriend's wealthy family. To escape her previous hardships, she chooses to lead a disciplined existence as a member of the Bishoya household. Women like her become the focus of societal gossip and scrutiny when they get into romantic relationships, highlighting the restrictive nature of deeply rooted traditional views. Moina-pehi, Pablo's youngest aunt, is caught up in the chaotic political turmoil of the time, and her death remains surrounded by uncertainty. The work vividly depicts the distressing

experience of Mamoni, a young woman who is victimized by four military soldiers through sexual assault, thereby illustrating the harsh and cruel realities that women face.

The novel *The Collector's Wife* by Mitra Phukan can be examined via a gyno-critical lens, focusing on the portrayal of female characters in literature written by women. Rukmini, the main character, challenges traditional gender norms and societal expectations. She rejects being limited to the position of only the collector's spouse, defying conventional notions of household duties and parenthood. Rukmini's reflection on a "male ovum donor" highlights the existing gender divide in society and the patriarchal standards that commodify women.

Both works emphasize the need to understand the experiences and viewpoints of women within the framework of Assamese society. Mitra Phukan's use of gyno-criticism offers a more profound examination of the female psyche, questioning traditional portrayals of women in literature. Both authors provide light on the challenges, determination, and defiance displayed by women within a societal structure influenced by established customs, politics, and subjugation. The accounts exemplify the diverse aspects of women's lives and highlight the significance of acknowledging their ability to influence their futures, even in the face of limitations imposed by their environment.

Rukmini's portrayal in *The Collector's Wife* first defies the dominant patriarchal standards and societal expectations, exhibiting a courageousness that progressively wanes as the story progresses. The repetitiveness of everyday existence, along with the context of political turmoil and widespread uncertainty, hurts her emotional well-being. Consequently, she struggles to preserve her identity and navigate her environment. Rukmini serves as the protagonist and narrator, providing a viewpoint that shapes the development of the plot. Nevertheless, the remaining female characters lack sufficient development, resulting in their emotions and perspectives being mostly unexplored. Rukmini's lack of understanding of the difficulties and issues encountered by ordinary women, particularly those in rural regions, may be due to her privileged upbringing outside Assam.

Rukmini's regression towards adhering to traditional gender norms, exemplified by her desire for children as a response to being labelled as infertile, highlights the societal constraints and expectations that weigh heavily on women. Although she first resists, she finally yields to these external influences, thereby demonstrating the profound impact that cultural standards can have on individuals, even those with great determination. The woman's fluctuating self-

assurance and indecisiveness while seeking advice from a gynaecologist highlight the deep-rooted societal taboos and stigmas associated with women's health and reproductive issues. This worry further exemplifies how patriarchal norms shape her decisions and actions.

Recognizing the multiple aspects of Rukmini's personality and the intricate social context she encounters is crucial. The internal conflicts and vulnerabilities she experiences illustrate the challenges women have when navigating a society that reinforces traditional standards and expectations. The story provides profound insights into the complex network of women's lives in Assamese society during that particular era, through Rukmini's journey. The film offers a subtle and detailed depiction of the complexities and inconsistencies that characterize women's lives and decisions in a socio-cultural environment influenced by conventional beliefs and gender norms.

...Rukmini was a barren woman...when a childless female took an undue interest in one's offspring, it was time to ward off the evil eye by going home as soon as possible, roasting mustard seeds on an open fire, murmuring mantras over the head of the child whose name was taken by the barren women. (167)

Indeed, Rukmini's portrayal in *The Collector's Wife* encapsulates the complex array of obstacles that women frequently encounter inside cultural structures. Her experience in married life is characterized by a strong feeling of being alone and a strong desire to become a mother, which amplifies her feelings of grief and a struggle with her sense of self. The challenges she faces are relatable to the collective encounters of women who confront the expectations imposed by cultural standards while endeavouring to achieve personal satisfaction and acknowledgement that extend beyond their duties as spouses or mothers.

Rukmini's adulterous relationship and her yearning for personal time beyond the boundaries of her marriage epitomize her pursuit of autonomy and self-exploration. The tale emphasizes her desire to create her own space and establish a unique identity separate from her connections with others. Mitra Phukan criticizes societal standards that confine women to traditional familial responsibilities or reduce them to mere appendages of their husbands through the figure of Rukmini. The work promotes the recognition of women as autonomous beings with their aspirations, desires, and intricacies. The portraits of Rukmini and Oholyajethai not only accurately represent the social conditions in Assam, but also strongly connect with the lives of women from other cultures and backgrounds. Their suffering and difficulties

reflect common themes that women experience while striving for self-awareness, empowerment, and fulfilment.

The novel, by depicting the challenges faced by these women, promotes the demand for a comprehensive and empowering environment for women in society. It necessitates acknowledging their distinctiveness, independence, and entitlements as individuals, rather than restricting them to predetermined roles and expectations. Mitra Phukan's portrayal of these female characters serves as a potent reminder of the imperative for gender parity and the importance of women's perspectives and opinions in both literature and society as a whole. The novel promotes a vision of a society in which women are not exclusively characterized by their connections or positions, but are esteemed as individuals with complex identities and ambitions.

Ordinary Life of Characters of Pukhan and Kashyap

Aruni Kashyap's novel, *The House with a Thousand Stories*, and Mitra Phukan's novel, *The Collector's Wife*, skillfully depict the current social conditions of Assamese society. Although Kashyap's narrative primarily revolves around rural life and Phukan's work primarily examines urban existence, both authors adeptly explore the complexities of human relationships, dynamics of parenting, friendships, the difficulties of love, and the pervasive presence of discrimination. Moreover, their narratives emphasize the interconnectedness between literature and the natural environment, highlighting a collective awareness of ecological concerns. The novels' settings in the Brahmaputra valley serve as heartbreaking reminders of the profound connection between daily life and the river that moulds it.

Both authors exhibit an unwavering dedication to depicting society in an unadorned manner, constructing small-scale representations that reflect the pain and challenges faced by individuals amid political turmoil and exploitation. Their storylines explore themes like as social class and caste, gender relations, disputes, demonstrations, and compassion, all rooted in a basis of reality. Kashyap and Phukan's portrayal of their characters' real experiences sheds light on current societal issues and legitimately challenges established standards, thus driving social change. Their depictions of marginalized and underrepresented sectors of society evoke readers' empathy and motivate them to address and correct social injustices.

Both Aruni Kashyap and Mitra Phukan can be considered genuine social realists, as their literary works aim to accurately depict the facts of their society and inspire good change.

By employing perceptive narrative techniques, they offer readers a glimpse into the lives of individuals manoeuvring through the intricacies of Assamese society, revealing the challenges and successes that define the experiences of common persons.

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